

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B398
 Date: 11 Sep 2008
 Take Off: 07:55:59
 Landing: 09:45:31
 Flight Time 1h 49m 32s

Campaign: TOFAMS (CPI Test) Flight

Operating Area: North Norfolk and the Wash

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Jon Taylor	Met Office	y
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	Y
6	Cloud Physics 2 / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	Y
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	CPI	James Dorsey	University of Manchester	
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				

Flight Track:

B398 Track 11-SEP-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B398
 Date: 11/9/08
 Project: TOFAMS (CPI Test) test
 Location: The Wash

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
074542		engine start	0.58 kft	113	
074727		power change	0.58 kft	113	
074924		taxy	0.57 kft	113	
074958		asp open	0.57 kft	067	
075559		T/O	0.57 kft	211	
080332	081801	Profile 1	10.0 - 23.9 kft	326	
082109	082236	Profile 2	23.9 - 22.5 kft	323	
082237	090144	Run 1.1	22.5 kft	321	
090629	091643	Run 2.1	11.5 kft	158	
091822	093443	Run 3.1	10.0 kft	318	
094531		Land	0.55 kft	212	at Cranfield

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B398 Track 11-SEP-08

Sortie Brief: CPI-test flight**Date: 11 Sept 2008****Flight Number: B398****TO time: 09.00z (duration 2 hours)****M.Sci: Jon Taylor**

Sortie Aims: To carry out a full airborne test of the CPI instrument in liquid, mixed phase and ice cloud on a number of straight and level runs (SLRs) at different altitudes. In previous APPRAISE-cloud missions in Germany during EUCAARI, the probe failed to work properly when airborne, but seemed to have no obvious faults when run on the ground. The probe has been serviced in Manchester and needs testing with an experienced operator before the C-check. If any problems are encountered this will enable the probe to be returned to the manufacturer for fixing before the APPRAISE-clouds December/January/February flying period, where it is a priority instrument.

Sortie Location: North Norfolk and the Wash.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of straight and level runs at a series of altitudes (and hence temperatures) within cloud, so that ice phase, mixed phase and liquid cloud are sampled. A profile up through cloud can be used to identify the cloud phases and so be used to determine suitable SLR altitudes. There should be full interaction between CPI operator and Mission Scientist so as to maximise the test flight objectives.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area.
- b) Carry out a profile within cloud up to FL280.
- c) Carry out a SLR at FL280 for 10minutes
- d) Descend to FL250 and carry out a 10minute SLR at FL250.
- e) Descend to FL220 and carry out a 10minute SLR at FL220
- f) Descend to FL190 and carry out a 10minute SLR at FL190
- g) Descend to FL160 and carry out a 10minute SLR at FL160
- h) Descend to FL130 and carry out a 10minute SLR at FL130
- i) Descend to transit altitude and return to Cranfield.

NB. The number of SLRs and their altitudes can be adjusted to fit in with the time constraints of the 2 hour flight, and to fit in with the cloud conditions encountered.

Key instruments and their operation

- Core Cloud Physics, CPI and 2DS, SP2.

B399 Sortie debrief

Date : 11th Sep 2008

Mission Scientist : Jon Taylor

This flight was to test the performance of the CPI probe following problems in Eucarri. The flight took place in the North Sea where an extensive layer of mixed phase and ice cloud was studied. The CPI was found to work perfectly well.

Alts & level
5000ft
FL115
FL200
FL225

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Taylor.

Flight No **B.398**.....

Date 11 SEP 08.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
075557					Take off
					cloud base 1000ft } alt water
					top 6500ft
080332	P1	FL100	327		Profile
080519		FL115			In same cloud ~ T ~ 0 deg C
080957					turn right in clouds on reciprocal
					back - in clear slot between
					cloud layers at FL115 and higher layers.
081215	P1	FL188	175		Restart continue ascent.
081401	P1	FL200			CI small ice + falling aggregates
					T = -18.94
					patchy cloud at FL200
0816	P1	FL225			In to cloud again T = -22°C.
					Small water drops
081801	P1	FL240			Interrupt P1 air bagging / end of P1.
082109	P2	FL200			By P2
		FL230			Small water / ice from CI
082237	P2/P1	FL225			End of P2 + start of P1
					Some ice accretion on pylons
					T = -21.76°C Td = -18.76°C (?)
					was -26°C
					large aggregates of big water - 2D
					seeing same. - CI
082858		FL225			less big water now. on both sides
083249	P1	FL225			back in big water / mixed phase T = -21.7

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Miss Sci: Jan Taylor

Flight No **B. 398**
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Date 11 SEP 08

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08309	R1	F225	161	52°36'N 18°6'W	Out of cloud at South Eastern end of run T = -21.8°C
083920	R1	F225	324		Large ice ~1000µm Both probes getting good data at this altitude. Large range of ice types plus big water.
084132					
084233	R1	F225			out of cloud at NW end of run.
		F225	147		Still in cloud mixed phase T = -21.9°C
084806	R1	F225	156		Out of cloud.
085533	R1	F225	315		Turn on reciprocal at same alt. T = -22.4°C Td = -26.86
090143	R1	F225			End of Run 1 descend now to get in to big water cloud.
		F415			End of descent.
090629	R2	F415	158		Start of Run 2 Mainly big water but some large columns falling through. T = -0.66°C
091043	R2.1	F415	161°		Out of cloud at SE end of run
091643	R2.1				End of R2.1 descend to get into thick cloud.
091822	R3.1	F415			Start of Run 3.1 T = -2.36°C in and out of big water clouds.
					CPI working well, believe that malfunction prompted flight may have been previous operator problem.
0927					Out of cloud

0929
093443

End of science - recover to Campobello

In cloud T = +1.76

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B398 **T/O:** 07:55:59
Date of flight: 11/09/08 **Land:** 09:45:31

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B398
Date of Flight: 11/09/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	12390 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 153128
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 27261 Blocks written = 27261 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 075000 End = 095000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc images ok. 2dp noisy – some images. Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 2dc 20 pages 2dp 59 pages

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b398_tas</p> <p>Start = 075000 End = 095000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 092441 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 2823</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b398_tas Y = (X+1) = b398_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B398
Date of Flight: 11/09/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_proccasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_proccasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b398_tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

Flight:

B398

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B398

Date: 11/09/08

Instruments

- 1.

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

MPDS

Satcom-H Calls

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html - Microsoft Intern...

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help SnagIt

Flight B398 08:32:33
 Heading 155 deg Speed 298 knots Height 22.5kft Press 418mb
 Lat 52°48.0'N Long 0°24.0'W Wind 229 ms-1/ 129 deg
 Temp -21.66C Dewpoint -18.86C

Current values

TRUE AIR SPEED	298.85	knots
MACH NO	0.48	-
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	251.5	K
ANGLE OF ATTACK	6.05	deg
ANGLE OF SIDESLIP	0.92	deg
NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	144.94	m s-1
EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	-177.97	m s-1
VERTICAL WIND COMPONENT	-68.05	m s-1
INS WIND SPEED	229.52	m s-1
INS WIND ANGLE	129.16	deg
STATIC PRESSURE	418.29	mb
PITOT STATIC PRESSURE	72.56	mb
TURB PROBE PITOT-STATIC	72.13	mb
TURB PROBE ATTACK DIFF	-3.04	mb
TURB PROBE SIDESLIP DIFF	1.87	mb
TURB PROBE ATTACK CHECK	99.71	mb
TURB PROBE SIDESLIP CHECK	114	mb
TURB PROBE DRY TAS	153.17	m s-1
TURB PROBE WET TAS	153.17	m s-1
TURB PROBE COR PITOT-STATIC	72.25	mb
GIN N VELOCITY	5.86	m s-1
GIN E VELOCITY	-111.74	m s-1
GIN D VELOCITY	68.82	m s-1
GIN ROLL	-0.15	deg
GIN PITCH	5.77	deg
GIN HEADING	155.44	deg
GIN RATE ABOUT LONG	131.23	deg s-1
GIN RATE ABOUT TRANS	0.05	deg s-1
GIN RATE ABOUT DOWN	0.04	deg s-1

http://192.168.101.71/plot/plot.html - Microsoft Intern...

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help SnagIt

Flight B398 08:57:56
 Heading 325 deg Speed 292 knots Height 22.5kft Press 418mb
 Lat 52°42.0'N Long 0°30.0'W Wind 264 ms-1/ 296 deg
 Temp -21.61C Dewpoint -21.54C

Current values

TRUE AIR SPEED	292.48	knots
MACH NO	0.47	-
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	251.55	K
ANGLE OF ATTACK	6.1	deg
ANGLE OF SIDESLIP	0.85	deg
NORTHWARDS WIND COMPONENT	-116.63	m s-1
EASTWARDS WIND COMPONENT	236.93	m s-1
VERTICAL WIND COMPONENT	80.92	m s-1
INS WIND SPEED	264.08	m s-1
INS WIND ANGLE	296.21	deg
STATIC PRESSURE	418.5	mb
PITOT STATIC PRESSURE	69.35	mb
TURB PROBE PITOT-STATIC	68.98	mb
TURB PROBE ATTACK DIFF	-3.11	mb
TURB PROBE SIDESLIP DIFF	1.54	mb
TURB PROBE ATTACK CHECK	95.01	mb
TURB PROBE SIDESLIP CHECK	108.92	mb
TURB PROBE DRY TAS	149.95	m s-1
TURB PROBE WET TAS	149.95	m s-1
TURB PROBE COR PITOT-STATIC	69.1	mb
GIN N VELOCITY	5.86	m s-1
GIN E VELOCITY	148.94	m s-1
GIN D VELOCITY	-81.02	m s-1
GIN ROLL	0.86	deg
GIN PITCH	6.1	deg
GIN HEADING	325.25	deg
GIN RATE ABOUT LONG	169.55	deg s-1
GIN RATE ABOUT TRANS	-0.26	deg s-1
GIN RATE ABOUT DOWN	0.05	deg s-1

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B398:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics In Flight	There appears to be only a blank log for this flight so not included
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet

AMS - not yet fitted

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	08 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_080558_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_090558_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_080605_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_090605_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_080608_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_090608_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_080602_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080911_r0_b398_090602_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.